

Recommended citation: Nagy, K. (2019). Critical media literacy in the engineering education. In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 805-816). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14656555.

Critical media literacy in the Education of Engineers

How can we tackle the social risks posed by algorithms?

K. Nagy

Budapest University of Technology and Economics
Faculty of Economic and Social Sciences
Budapest, Hungary

Conference Key Areas: Strong demand for democratic involvement in educational processes, Sustainability reflecting the complexity of modern society

Keywords: fake news, online platforms, algorithms, learning by doing

ABSTRACT

Digital technology has profoundly changed the information ecosystem and the way people access information. It is a new phenomenon of the online environment that the operation of online platforms contributes to putting online disinformation and fake news into a new dimension. The paper presents a higher education course which aims to structure the social, social psychological, economical and regulatory aspects and dimensions of the online disinformation phenomenon. The complexity of the information environment in the modern society is presented in this framework. The course focuses on the big internet intermediaries' operation and the impact of their operation. The objective of the course is to ensure that the training of engineers and software developers includes the relevant market, sociological, political scientific, social psychological, and legal/regulatory knowledge that will help foster a responsible attitude in the persons who are behind the creation of the relevant algorithms. The core message of the course is that developing an algorithm to organize the information flow is a kind of regulation, which influences the condition of the public debate and the freedom of expression.

A special pedagogical, methodological approach, based on cooperative learning and learning by doing techniques is presented in the paper. This approach prepares students for creating a policy paper against online disinformation at the end of the course. Besides this, the main element of the methodological approach is that the students' skills to tackle disinformation and propaganda are improved as well. The course adds an interdisciplinary approach to the engineering education, making students understand all aspects which influence the impact that online platforms and algorithms have on the increase of online disinformation in the information environment.

1. INTRODUCTION

How do algorithms that perform internet traffic management shape people's media usage and news consumption patterns? What is the impact of the mass of fake news in the online space on the operation of public discourse? What role might algorithms play in managing the risk stemming from the fake news phenomenon? What ethical norms and social values are reflected in the way these algorithms work? What role and importance could an overview of the social, economic and regulatory dimensions of the information technology ecosystem play in training engineers? These are some of the issues that our course entitled *The regulatory issues of online platforms¹ in the context of the fake news phenomenon* seeks to explore.

In the early stages of the internet, it appeared as if the world wide web would help advance democratic culture and democratize public discourse by opening up the public space to every individual, allowing them to speak directly to everyone else and by expanding the possibility to access information to a hitherto unprecedented and previously inconceivable degree.² However, these days it has become apparent that the new communication environment generated by the internet is not all positive, that its impact is not limited to fostering a more democratic culture of communication. It is at the same time also a source of a variety of new and previously unanticipated social risks. The rapid mass proliferation of fake news in online communication is a preeminent example of the variety of risks that plague democratic discourse in the age of online communication.

The underlying cause of this phenomenon appears to be that the information flow bottlenecks have been transformed by the internet, undermining in the process the power of media players that previously operated as gatekeepers, so to speak, in the dissemination of information³. Editorial work based on the professional and ethical standards of journalism worked as a filter of sorts sifting through and removing vast quantities of misleading information and fake news that might otherwise have been published. The dissolution of the gatekeeper structure simultaneously resulted in the loss of the filter mechanisms against such harmful and damaging contents and the risks they pose for society. At the same time, we are witnessing the emergence of new types of controlling mechanisms in the form of online services, such as the algorithm-based search engines and algorithm-based editorial control over social media platforms⁴. Since these services have substantial influence on how we access information, and thus on the totality of the information that is published in public discourse, we can regard these as the new gatekeepers of information flows. The strength and value of these services is based on the information flows that are individually customised by the algorithms. The algorithms select between incoming information – reducing the array of information that is potentially available to the given individual – and convey pre-selected information to any given individual based on the personality profile they have compiled about that person by tracking their digital footprint. Managing the flow of information by way of algorithms has become so dominant over the past years that it has given rise to the concept of an algorithmic

society, which may be more useful in capturing present-day society than the previously used categories of network and platform society. According to Balkin's definition, an algorithmic society is a "society organized around social and economic decisionmaking by algorithms, robots, and AI agents, who not only make the decisions but also, in some cases, carry them out"⁵. An algorithmic society is characterised by the grand social media platforms that connect nations and average persons, and by their reliance on algorithms and artificial intelligence to control the masses⁶, where "algorithms mediate almost all interaction and content that we do not experience directly, face-to-face and in person"⁷.

Balkin also includes the wide-ranging collection of individual data that helps monitor and keep track of individuals among the key features of an algorithmic society, and he also mentions the appearance of new forms of discrimination and manipulation. The new gatekeepers of the underlying information flows are the multinational corporations which dispose over the infrastructure that serves as the conduit of online communication. It is the decisions taken by these corporations and the workings of the algorithms designed by them that "govern the digital spaces in which people communicate with each other" and "our practical ability to speak is subject to the decisions of [these] private infrastructure owners"⁸.

The transformation of the infocommunications environment described above gives an entirely new dimension to the phenomenon of fake news and false information. A striking change is the rapid mass proliferation of fake news in online communication; the underlying cause is found in the mechanisms and key phenomena that govern the operations of the information ecosystem. The inclusion of users in content production and – through the social media platforms – in content dissemination has served to supplant the previously dominant method for filtering information, which rested on editorial practices and standards. Vast amounts of information appear in public that circumvent the traditional methods of information filtering, and the ability of traditional mass media to act as information gatekeepers is seriously diminished. A technological/infrastructural reason for the shift to the new dimension is that the present info-communications environment holds out the possibility of spreading information extremely rapidly – and that is true for fake news, too. The information flows, which have become personalised with the help of algorithms, have engendered an architecture that helps access information that meshes with the individuals' prejudices and preconceptions of the world, thus reinforcing their prior worldviews. The phenomenon of the information filter bubble is one consequence of the individually customised flow of information⁹. Its result is that the information stream that we personally encounter has been pre-filtered based on our previous preferences. This individually customised information stream will not even remotely present all the relevant information on a subject matter, it will only show a narrow segment of the information out there. The segment of information that we do actually encounter will orient itself along the line delineated by our previous online activities based on our personal profile, which was created by algorithms.

Thus, the algorithm-based steering of information by online platforms reinforces the previously observed attitude that governs people's acceptance of information, which suggests that they have a predilection for views and information that meshes with or

matches their own, while they tend to disregard information that does not fit into their own view of the world. Such a consumer attitude also favours the spread of fake news. It is worth emphasising that “social media are particularly effective at directly reaching large numbers of people, while simultaneously micro-targeting individuals with personalized messages.¹⁰ Social media have gone from being the natural infrastructure for sharing collective grievances and coordinating civic engagement, to being a computational tool for social control, manipulated by canny political consultants, and available to politicians in democracies and dictatorships alike”¹¹.

In addition to the problems stemming from the way the broader infrastructure operates, the business model of online platforms and the way they operate in the market also contributes to the mass proliferation of fake news by virtue of the fact that information traffic management is click-sensitive and fosters the rapid dissemination of sensationalistic, click, like and share-bait contents, and correspondingly it also offers a profitable business model for fake news factories.¹²

Needless to say, the online platforms and algorithms that organise the communication on these platforms are not alone in bearing the responsibility for the mass spread of fake news – nevertheless, the way these services operate and their features play a major role in boosting the phenomenon of fake news to an entirely new level, and correspondingly they could also potentially play a major role in combatting fake news.

2. WHY IS IT IMPORTANT FOR THE TRAINING OF ENGINEERS TO INCLUDE A DISCUSSION OF THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONTEXT OF THE FAKE NEWS PHENOMENON?

The rapid and mass proliferation of fake news is a complex phenomenon, depending on the perspective one brings to the issue it could be captured as a contemporary problem of either politics and/or media. Technology reinforces the impact of these unresolved problems, and information traffic management systems that are not designed with sufficient care and circumspection could result in massive social risks and harmful side effects. At the same time, it is also true that technological instruments can be used in combatting online disinformation. Today, artificial intelligence can be used to filter out fake profiles on social media platforms that are engaged in coordinated disinformation, while algorithm-based information traffic management allows us to reduce the visibility of fake news. It is thus of the utmost importance whether the companies or engineers that develop the algorithms are cognisant of the social consequences of information traffic management. Similarly, the ethical principles and norms that influence the work of the developers in designing algorithm-based editorial control are also vital. The social responsibility associated with this new type of control is predicated on a knowledge and understanding of how public discourse and the socio-economic context of the media environment operate. This also means that the training of engineers may increasingly call for an approach that takes into consideration the anticipated social impact of technological development, with the corollary awareness of the economic and sociological skills that are needed to understand the relevant social phenomena. This approach is also reinforced by an expert document released by the Council of Europe,¹³ which posits that an indirect factor in the design of algorithms ought to be the goal of ensuring that those who produce these algorithms “are aware of the legal challenges, ethical dilemmas and

human rights concerns that arise from automated data-processing and decisionmaking techniques. An instrument to achieve such goals could consist of standardised professional ethics or forms of licensing systems for data engineers and algorithm designers, similar to those that exist for professions like doctors, lawyers or architects”.

3. THE COURSE ENTITLED *REGULATORY ISSUES CONCERNING ONLINE PLATFORMS IN THE CONTEXT OF THE FAKE NEWS PHENOMENON*

The Department of Business Law at the Faculty of Economic and Social Sciences (abbreviated as GTK in Hungarian) of the Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME) launched the course entitled *Regulatory issues concerning online platforms in the context of the fake news phenomenon* in the academic year 2018/2019. The course was intended as a pilot project for GTK students. Among other things, the goal was to turn this pilot project into a standard part of the engineering curriculum at the university. It is a one-semester course with two weekly class hours. In terms of its thematic structure and methodological approach, this course qualifies as an innovative element in the educational programme offered by the faculty. It seeks to furnish students with knowledge about a contemporary problem, to wit the mass proliferation of fake news in the online environment, using an interdisciplinary approach to present the risks for society that they give rise to. The basic objective of the course is to review the economic and social aspects of the fake news phenomenon, which has recently become exacerbated to such an extent that it has risen to an entirely new quality and level. In this context, the focus is especially on identifying the roles of online platforms and the algorithms that serve as their information traffic management system, as well as raising awareness about the social responsibility of platform providers and discussing the relevant dilemmas of professional ethics.

3.1. The structure of the course and the outline of the topics

The course is based on three major pillars. The first pillar organises and structures those technology, economics, market, politics and media-related issues and phenomena that had an impact on shifting fake news into their new current dimension. At the same time it also explores the social risks and threats stemming from the rapid mass proliferation of fake news. It reviews the regulatory framework that applies to fake news contents, that is it explores the limits that the existing legal regulations impose on the public dissemination of misleading and false information. As part of the discussion of the relevant regulations, the review of the pertinent rules concerning the regulations of online platforms with respect to their handling of fake news will receive special attention. The discussion will also highlight those social values and objectives that can only be realised with the active involvement and cooperation of platform providers and technology developers, such as for example the transparency of their algorithms or, closely related to the latter, the issue of the research community’s access to data that is pertinent to our understanding of the fake news phenomena” The second pillar is the issue of internet governance. The objective of the course is to review the regulatory processes that pertain to the operation of the internet and to discuss the questions of professional ethics concerning technological development in their broader regulatory context. The course will also present the efforts at tackling the issue at the level of the European Union. It will discuss the expert consultation

procedures that have been ongoing in the EU over the past years to shine a light on the details of the efforts to identify solutions at the European level.¹⁴ The focus on the applied aspects of the regulatory process will provide the students with an idea of the potential methods and workings of internet governance. The regulatory process that is implemented in the framework of governance is based on the mutual cooperation of stakeholders (e.g. market players, the state and academia), and the eventual regulatory solutions in such an approach are designed in the complex network of cooperation between state, economic and social players.¹⁵ The course models the underlying regulatory process, and the final output of this effort is a policy paper jointly drawn up by the students, which will include a package of strategic solutions against online disinformation.

The third pillar is the development of critical media literacy. The relevant skills are all part of the 4C framework: critical thinking, communication, collaboration and creativity.¹⁶ Among the various competencies that make up the broader concept of media literacy, critical media literacy stresses the importance of bringing a critical perspective to media use and information consumption. The key features of today's information environment, i.e. the confluence of the sheer mass of information, the relative ease of manipulating digital contents, and the disintegration of the previous system of information gatekeepers, necessitate a higher level of critical skills than previously. If someone is unable to properly sift through the mass of information they receive, and to effectively analyse, evaluate and synthesise the information thus collected, or if they are unable to properly communicate their messages to others, they could easily become vulnerable and readily manipulated in the realm of digital communication. Critical thinking also includes the ability to avail oneself of the skills one has acquired to solve problems and to properly use data and facts in the process, which is why critical thinking and problem-solving skills are frequently interrelated.¹⁷ The course uses exercises to improve the students' critical thinking.

Communication is developed through collaboration in this course. "Collaboration is a process through which a group of people productively explore their ideas to search for a solution that extends into the exploration and generation of new concepts".¹⁸ In our presentation of the course methodology, we will also provide a more detailed discussion of how communication and collaboration skills will be improved; for the time being, we only wish to stress here that we will typically use small group cooperative learning techniques to work through the curriculum and convey the relevant skills.

Creativity can also be described as thinking differently or, to put it metaphorically, as "thinking outside the box". Creativity means imagination, the formulation of new thoughts, solutions and unique ideas. In the course, the development of creativity will play an especially important role in drafting the joint policy paper, where the students will apply the knowledge and skills they acquired during the classes to come up with a package of solutions to tackle the mass proliferation of fake news.

To review the thematic structure of the course, we have chosen the method of presenting the details of individual topics by laying out the questions that we will discuss during the respective sessions.

1. Introduction: the phenomenon of fake news in the algorithmic society

What is fake news? What definition could be used to accurately capture the concept of false and misleading information that poses a risk to society, and on what type of fake news contents should one focus on in the process of coming up with solutions? (Typology of fake news and online disinformation)

Fake news has always existed. What factors have elevated the problem to a whole new level?

2. The technological context of the fake news phenomenon: network science, artificial intelligence, algorithms

What technological tools help spread the mass dissemination of fake news, and what tools might technology provide to combat fake news? (recommender systems, semantic technology, fake news-spreading bots, algorithmic news analysis)

3. The social and news market context of the fake news phenomenon and its impact on public discourse

What are the media-related causes and background of the fake news phenomenon? (changes in news consumption and information patterns, the transformation of the news market)

Why do fake news spread? (psychological and social psychology background)

What impact does the mass proliferation of fake news have on the functioning of public discourse and on the quality of democracy? (fragmented public discourse, emotion-governed public debates, a general loss of trust in the media)

4. The economic and market context of the fake news phenomenon

What economic and business reasons might explain the mass proliferation of fake news? (the mechanisms that govern online advertising: personalised advertising and the possibility of monetising fake news contents in the online space)

5. Fake news and content management regulation

Does the law prohibit the public dissemination of lies? Are we living in the post-truth era?

What tools does the law provide us with to stem the spread of fake news? (freedom of expression, lies concerning specific persons – defamation, media law instruments)

6. The regulatory framework of online platforms – regulatory provisions that are relevant with respect to the fake news phenomenon, with a special focus on the regulatory universe of Facebook

What is the responsibility of online platforms for contents published by their users? Can online platforms regulate autonomously? Are Facebook's activities involving the removal of contents and blocking of users lawful?

<p>7. Self-regulation mechanisms: The answers and initiatives of online platforms</p> <p>What measures and service functions do online platforms deploy to reduce the level of fake news contents published on their platforms? (action to combat coordinated misleading communication, ranking policy, solutions to demonetise fake news contents)</p>
<p>8. EU policies with an impact on the operation of online platforms: regulatory approaches, pending initiatives, proposed solutions</p> <p>What were the key stages over the past two years of the European Commission's policies aimed at combatting online disinformation? (internet governance, official EU documents, the self-regulation documents of online platforms)</p>
<p>9. Overview of problems: defining the issues that a set of solutions to tackle online disinformation must address</p> <p>Assigning the issues to small groups that address them individually.</p>
<p>10. Developing critical media literacy: The possibilities and practice of strengthening the consumer side. (Reviewing the credibility and reliability of information, the practice of critical questions, analysis of sources and fact-checking practices)</p>
<p>11. Presenting policy materials concerning individual policy areas – results of the small group problem-solving exercise</p>
<p>12. Using teamwork to develop a package of solutions against online disinformation (joint policy paper)</p>

3.2. The methodology of the course

Diversity

The course will realise the envisioned multi-layered development of student skills with the combined deployment of diverse methodological elements, which will include regular teacher presentations, small-group in-class exercises, small group research outside class, individual desk research, drafting and giving presentations; as well as a large-group structured exercise.

Personal media experience and individual information consumption patterns

The starting point of the underlying pedagogical approach that we have adopted for the course is to draw on personal experience and individual information consumption patterns – as well as the relevant personal experience – and integrate these into the teaching/learning process. The students' recalling of their own experiences will help the instructors convey the relevant knowledge about the given topic and to share the relevant experiences within the group. At the same time, no substantial progress can be attained in developing media literacy without bringing the students' own experiences out in the open: a reflection on one's own information consumption and

media experience helps the emergence of a more deliberate and reflective media consumption.

Topicality, current developments

The course will also present the various regulatory approaches towards internet governance and it will track the current developments that try to get a handle on the fake news phenomenon. To enhance the success of this effort, the course will also look at the rapidly changing technological and business environment, and in the process of discussing these we will also refer to current events, news, and new features developed by the various platforms as part of their effort to combat fake news, as well as the evaluation of the aforementioned. We will discuss current and topical research, such as for example surveys of consumption patterns and media markets, statistics, and the continuously changing service functions of online platforms and recent changes in their terms of agreement with their users. If Facebook adds a new feature aimed at reducing the visibility of fake news, that will also be a part of our discussions, and the same holds for the assessment of the most recent transparency report on the deletion and blocking activities of Facebook. In addition to reading and interpreting the texts, such classroom activities also offer excellent opportunities for games that help us work through specific problems by looking at the event from the perspective of various stakeholders. One example is the exercise in which small groups of students take the role of Facebook decision-makers who need to come up with a package of solutions in response to the adoption of detailed German regulations concerning online platforms. These solutions must allow Facebook to operate without violating the new law and to avoid becoming subject to the sanctions set out in the law.

Using multimedia materials for education

The course also relies on scenes from films that are particularly apt for demonstrating certain phenomena under discussions. In the previous semester we used scenes from two films on topical issues, the documentary *The Cleaners*¹⁹ and the movie *Brexit*²⁰. In addition to the films, we also use online teaching interfaces in the course. The website News Literacy Project²¹ Checkology.org and the e-learning curriculum (alhirvadasz.hu) created by a Hungarian investigative news portal²² are aimed at improving critical media literacy. Assessment

The assessment of the students' work and progress during the course will orient itself along the lines of the course objective. The assessment is based in equal parts on two distinct elements: a mid-term paper written about the course materials at the end of the two-thirds segment of the course as well as the evaluation of the research/presentation exercise.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The fake news problem has shifted to a whole new level due to a complex confluence of social, economic and technological developments. This new informational environment that has emerged as a consequence of the pervasive use of algorithms harbours new types of risks for the workings of our public discourse and the democratic values that govern society. Exposing and understanding these risks is a basic precondition for the ability of the companies and developers who are responsible for the operation of the algorithms to define the infrastructural framework of online

communication in line with consensual social norms and ethical principles. The most fundamental objective of the course presented here is to ensure that the training of engineers and software developers include the market, sociological, political scientific, social psychological, and legal/regulatory knowledge that will help foster a responsible attitude in the persons who are behind the creation of the relevant algorithms. In addition to the academic/technical knowledge, the course will also place a substantial emphasis on developing the students' skills, since critical media literacy not only serves to increase the students' awareness when they consume information but also seeks to convey the possibilities for and potential impact of technological manipulations.

REFERENCES

- [1] Platforms are services that operate in the online space and rely on automated technology for managing data traffic in the interest of generating and maintaining business, commercial and interpersonal contacts between users. Van Dijck, J., Poell, T. (2016) Understanding the promises of online health platforms. *Big Data & Society*, January-June 1-11
- [2] Green, S. (1999): A plague on the panopticon: surveillance and power in the global information society. *Information, Communication and Society*, 2
- [3] Jenkins, H. (2006) *Convergence Culture: Where old and new media collide*. New York, NYU press⁴ Cheung, A. (2015) Searching for search engine liability in the autocomplete era. In: András Koltay (ed.) *Comparative Perspectives on the Fundamental Freedom of Expression* Budapest, Wolters Kluwer
- [4] Balkin, J. M. (2017) The Three Laws of Robotics in the Age of Big Data. *78 Ohio State Law Journal* 1217-1241
- [5] Balkin, J. M. (2018) Free Speech in the Algorithmic Society: Big Data, Private Governance, an New School Speech Regulation U.C. Davis Law Review, Vol. 51, Issue 3 (February 2018), pp. 1149-1210
- [6] Wolley, S.C., Howard, P.N., (2016). Political Communication, Computational Propaganda, and Autonomous Agents. *International Journal of Communication*, 10 (Special Issue), 20. 4882–4890⁸ Balkin, J. M. (2018) i.m.
- [7] Pariser, Eli (2011) *The Filter Bubble: How the New Personalized Web Is Changing What We Read and How We Think*. London, Penguin

- [8] Challenging Truth and Trust: A Global Inventory of Organized Social Media Manipulation Oxford
- [9] University research program. Available at:
<https://blogs.oii.ox.ac.uk/wpcontent/uploads/sites/93/2018/07/ct2018.pdf> ¹¹ Wolley, S.C., Howard, P.N., (2016) i.m.
- [10] Allcott, H., Gentzkow, M. (2017) Social Media and Fake News in the 2016 Election Journal of
- [11] Economic Perspectives Volume 31 Number 2 pp. 211-236
- [12] DGI (2017)12
 Study the human rights dimension of automated data processing techniques (in particular algorithms) and possible regulatory implications. Available at:
<https://edoc.coe.int/en/internet/7589-algorithms-andhuman-rights-study-on-the-human-rights-dimensions-of-automated-data-processing-techniques-and-possibleregulatory-implications.html>
- [13] Digital Single Market - Fake news and online disinformation
<https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/fake-news-disinformation>
- [14] Schuppert, G. (2010) Mi a media governance? [What is media governance?] in: Polyák Gábor (ed.) Médiapolitikai szöveggyűjtemény [Collection of texts on media policy]. Budapest, AKTI-Gondolat 153-167
- [15] Keane,T., Keane, W. F., Blicblau A. S. (2016) Beyond traditional literacy: Learning and transformative practices using ICT Education and Information Technologies July 2016, Volume 21, Issue 4, pp 769–781
- [16] Germaine, R., Richards, J., Koeller, M., Schubert-Irastorza, C. (Purposeful Use of 21st Century Skills in Higher Education (2016) Journal of Research in Innovative Teaching, 9(1), pp. 19-29
- [17] Reeve, E. M. (2016) 21st century skills needed by students in technical and vocational education and training (TVET) Asian International Journal of Social Sciences Volume 16 Issue 4 October - December 2016 pp. 65-82

[18] Keane, T., Keane, W. F., Blicblau A. S. (2016) i.m.

[19] <https://www.imdb.com/title/tt7689936/>

[20] <https://www.imdb.com/title/tt8425058/>

[21] <https://newslit.org/>

[22] <https://english.atlatszo.hu/>